

CLASSIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION OF BASIC EMOTIONS

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Abstract: *This article explores the significance, manifestation, and directionality of emotions, which exhibit different cultural specifics as reflected in language and speech. Emotions themselves and the conditions that evoke them can also vary. In the study of intercultural communication and its peculiarities, it is essential to interpret various manifestations of emotions, especially those differing in meaning, directionality, or degree of expressiveness.*

Keywords: *Basic emotion, semiotic systems of emotions, linguistics of emotions, emotive vocabulary, classification of emotions.*

The history of studying and classifying basic emotions is one of the most multifaceted and long-standing, spanning not just decades but centuries of analysis. Over time, emotions have differentiated, forming various specific forms that differ in their manifestations, patterns of occurrence, and ways of organization. The constant dynamics and diversity of emotional development give rise to numerous questions and opposing views on the differentiation of emotional phenomena. To provide the most comprehensive and objective representation of classifications of basic emotional phenomena, one must start with defining emotion. According to K. E. Izard, "Emotion is something that is experienced as a feeling, which motivates, organizes, and directs perception, thinking, and action" [Izard 2000: 156].

Y. D. Apresyan describes emotion as "a state conditioned by the situation that a person has perceived or observed" [Apresyan 1995: 37–65]. In psychology, emotions are understood as a psychological state expressed through human experiences and serve to assess the world surrounding the individual [Shishkoedov 2009: 120]. L. A. Weinstein, in his textbook on general psychology, defines the term "emotion" (from the Latin *emovere* – to excite, to stir) as "a special group of mental processes and states in which a person's subjective relationship to external and internal events in their life is expressed" [Weinstein 2009: 275].

In other words, emotion is an experience or state triggered by external or internal experiences, perceptions of an individual. Emotions can be expressed through physiological exteriorization (such as laughter, tears, blushing, or smiling) or verbalization—expressing or describing an emotion [Shakhovsky 2019: 59].

Thus, there are at least two semiotic systems for emotions—body language and verbal language. The physiological semiotic system is more reliable, direct, intense,

and sincere in expression than verbal language, and it is also more adequately decoded by the recipient. Many aspects of life are difficult to convey through words; the semantic space of language does not fully cover the entire world. When expressing and communicating our emotions, we sometimes encounter situations where the precision of language in conveying emotions is far from ideal. Additionally, verbal identification of emotions is often subjective [Diller 1992: 26].

The same emotion can be expressed differently by different people depending on various factors (for example, the context, place, or interlocutor can influence word choice). A. Heller noted that emotions are always situational and cognitive [Bonheim 1992: 47], and thus the choice of linguistic means to express them is also situational.

As L. G. Babenko writes, the difficulty in studying the language of emotions may be explained by the uniqueness and complexity of the object of study itself—emotions. Emotions are inseparable from the person, just like other evaluative tools, and thus the vocabulary used to express emotions belongs to the "human" sphere. "Emotions have a twofold way of reflecting in language. First, they appear in language as emotional accompaniment, emotional coloring, arising from the speaker's emotional state breaking through into speech in the form of emotional evaluations. Second, emotions are reflected by linguistic signs as an objectively existing reality" [Babenko 1989: 11]. The complexity of organizing emotive vocabulary can be reflected through the principle of polyparadigmaticity, meaning that emotive vocabulary is formed at the intersection of different lexical paradigms (denotative-ideographic, structural-semantic, cognitive-discursive, functional) [Babenko 2018: 452].

Since this study focuses on the connection between language and emotion, the concept of "linguistics of emotion" needs to be introduced. V. I. Shakhovsky defined the linguistics of emotion as a discipline formed at the intersection of linguistics and psychology, studying the connection between language and emotions. Regarding the issues in the linguistics of emotion, V. I. Shakhovsky identified the following key problems:

- Typology of emotive signs used to express different emotions;
- The influence of emotional types on the formation and understanding of the linguistic worldview;
- Communication of emotions;
- The problem of naming the same emotion in different languages;
- National and cultural specifics of expressing diverse emotions;
- Criteria of emotiveness in language and its signs;

- The relationship between paralinguistics and linguistics of emotion;
 - The influence of emotional emancipation on linguistic processes;
 - Emotional coloring of the studied text;
 - Emotive meaning space of the linguistic personality and emotive semantic space of the language;
 - Lexicography and linguodidactics of emotiveness;
 - Pragmatics of expressing and describing immediate, past, and others' emotions
- [Shakhovsky 2013: 78].

V. I. Shakhovsky divides emotive vocabulary into three groups:

1. Vocabulary expressing emotional attitude (e.g., to love, to dislike);
2. Vocabulary expressing emotional state (e.g., offended, irritated);
3. Vocabulary expressing emotional characteristics (e.g., baby, imp).

[Shakhovsky 2019: 162].

Currently, there are various classifications and descriptions of basic emotions. This diversity of opinions, definitions, and classifications is due to the high dynamics and diversity of emotions. Different authors often classify emotions from different perspectives, in different study areas, and under different conditions. Let's review some of these classifications.

Paul Ekman defined "basic emotions" based on two characteristics:

1. Such emotions are discrete (i.e., they can be fundamentally different from each other in terms of facial expression, physiology, and the causes that trigger them);

2. These emotions evolved during adaptation [Ekman, Cordaro 2011: 364].

Ekman created a list of criteria for basic emotions. According to him, if an emotion meets all (or almost all) of these criteria, it can be considered basic. These criteria include:

- Distinctive universal signals;
 - Distinctive physiology;
 - Automatic appraisal;
 - Distinct universals in preceding events;
 - Presence in other primates;
 - Ability to begin quickly;
 - Potentially short-lived;
 - Spontaneous appearance;
 - Distinctive thoughts, memories, and images;
 - Distinctive subjective experience;

- Information filtering (allowing information that supports the emotion);
- The object of emotion is not limited;
- Emotion can be either constructive or destructive [Ekman, Cordaro 2011: 365].

In the book by Paul Ekman and D. Cordaro *What is meant by calling emotions basic*, the following list of basic emotions is presented:

1. Amusement
2. Anger
3. Contempt
4. Disgust
5. Embarrassment [Ekman, Cordaro 2011: 365].

Emotional experiences can be divided into:

- Positive emotions;
- Negative emotions;
- Ambivalent emotions.

The main function of positive emotions is to maintain contact with a positive event. Positive emotions are associated with the approach response to a beneficial stimulus. Negative emotions are characterized by a withdrawal reaction, breaking contact with harmful or dangerous stimuli. Negative emotions are considered to play a more crucial biological role because they help ensure survival. Ambivalent emotions are contradictory emotional experiences, often tied to mixed feelings toward an object, i.e., simultaneous rejection and acceptance [Weinstein 2009: 276].

V. K. Vilyunas proposed a functional classification of emotions, based on their role in regulating activity. He considered emotions as mediators between needs and the activities aimed at fulfilling those needs. According to this criterion, emotions are divided into:

1. Leading emotions – experiences that become motives, leading emotions precede activities, motivating them, and determine their overall direction.
2. Derivative emotions – experiences arising during the activity, significant situationally, expressing the subject's attitude toward specific conditions or situations.

Depending on their degree of voluntariness, emotions can be voluntary or involuntary. Voluntariness of emotional response represents a continuous scale with varying degrees of expression. Emotions can also be classified based on their origin into innate (instinctual responses) and acquired (shaped by individual experience) [Vilyunas 1990: 176].

E. P. Ilyin proposed his classification of basic emotional types, considering the expressive component of emotional reactions and the criteria for systematizing emotions:

1. Emotions of expectation and prognosis (anxiety, worry, fear);
2. Frustration emotions (annoyance, disappointment);
3. Communicative emotions (shame, joy);
4. Affective-cognitive emotional complexes (interest, surprise, sense of humor);
5. Emotional states arising during activity (boredom, stress) [Ilyin 2001: 195].

Y. D. Apresyan identified five phases of emotional development:

1. Primary cause – mental or physical perception of a situation;
2. Cause – intellectual evaluation of the situation from the perspective of its desirability or undesirability for the subject;
3. Emotion – a state triggered by the situation and intellectual evaluation of the situation;
4. Desire to prolong or suppress the cause of the emotion, conditioned by the evaluation or the emotion itself;
5. External manifestation of emotion [Apresyan 1995a: 567].

K. E. Izard distinguished the following "fundamental emotions":

1. Interest – a positive emotional state that promotes knowledge acquisition and motivates learning.
2. Joy – a positive emotional state connected to social interactions, overcoming obstacles, and achieving goals.
3. Surprise – emotional reaction to unexpected events.
4. Suffering – a negative emotional state associated with unmet needs, disappointment, and failures.
5. Anger – a negative emotional state often experienced as an affect.
6. Disgust – a negative emotional state triggered by objects conflicting with the subject's principles.
7. Contempt – a negative emotional state arising from the discrepancy between the subject's and object's views or behavior.
8. Fear – a negative emotional state associated with perceived threats.
9. Shame – a negative state resulting from one's actions or thoughts not meeting the expectations of others.

10. Embarrassment – emotional state of vulnerability in social situations [Izard 2007: 365].

These fundamental emotions, when combined, create complex emotional states, for example, anxiety may combine anger, fear, guilt, and interest. Each emotion is the basis for a range of states with varying degrees of intensity (e.g., joy can manifest as delight, contentment, happiness, elation, etc.) [Izard 2007: 365].

To use these classifications most effectively, it is essential to delve into the meaning of emotional concepts.

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